

MODERN STATE OF ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND USE OF AIR-COOLING SYSTEMS IN BUILDINGS

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Abstract: This article provides information on the current state of building cooling and the energy consumption of buildings. This information provides information on the energy problems between the end of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century, emissions and the climate changes that cause them. The use of renewable energy resources, especially solar heating and cooling devices, is promoted for efficient cooling of buildings.

Key words: air conditioning, solar energy, cooling system, residential buildings.

In recent years, the demand for cooling buildings has been increasing rapidly worldwide. According to the International Energy Agency (IEA), the buildings sector accounts for about 30%–32% of the world's energy consumption. About 20% of the electricity used in buildings is used for air conditioning systems. Therefore, the use of renewable energy sources (RES) in building cooling systems is one of the most pressing issues in the world. If the electricity consumption for cooling systems continues to grow at this rate, then by 2050, the electricity consumption for cooling buildings will increase threefold [1]. As a result of the expansion of urban areas and electricity use, as well as the decline in the cost of air conditioners, the global market for domestic air conditioners has expanded significantly in many developed countries. Currently, the number of air conditioners in use worldwide exceeds 2 billion, most of which are installed in residential and commercial buildings. According to IEA forecasts, this figure could exceed 5 billion by 2050 [1]. This is an increase of 1.21 and 3.28 billion, respectively, compared to 2015. As a result, by 2050, domestic air conditioning and refrigeration will account for approximately 10% of electricity consumption. The use of cooling systems in buildings has increased further due to the warm weather conditions observed in 2024–2025. As a result, electricity consumption in the buildings sector has increased by more than 5% in one year. Experts estimate that the increase in demand for cooling technologies is placing additional strain on energy systems. In addition, such a large increase will significantly contribute to greenhouse gas emissions [2]. According to data, greenhouse gas emissions increased by 1.1 times from 2010 to 2024, which led to a significant increase in the average temperature of the Earth's surface in recent years. As a result of excessive consumption of minerals from 1750 to 2000, the concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere increased by 32%, and the concentration of CH₄ by 151% [3]. In 2024, the average temperature of the Earth's surface increased by a record 1.5°C, and in addition, from 2015 to 2025 it increased by 1.3°C. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, the average global temperature is expected to increase significantly by the end of the 21st century [4]. According to Chen et al. [5], the total concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere increased from 285 parts per million in 1850 to 415 parts per million in 2020, resulting in a global average temperature increase of 1.2°C. If global greenhouse gas emissions are significantly reduced by 2050, it is possible to limit the global average temperature to 1.5°C. To achieve net-zero CO₂ emissions between 2030 and 2050, a reduction of CO₂ emissions of at least 45% compared to 2010 levels is required [6].

In developing countries, indoor temperatures increase dramatically during the summer season due to high outdoor temperatures and poor building architecture. Overheating indoors and outdoors has a significant impact on thermal comfort, human health, peak demand for electricity for cooling, and the energy economy of the world and countries. In June 2022, temperatures exceeded 40°C in the Middle East, North Africa, Europe, and Asia, and this record figure remained for a long time [7].

Therefore, cooling indoor air and reducing outdoor temperatures is one of the most common ways to combat overheating. In several countries, buildings consume one third of their energy production, of which 1.24 PVh of energy is spent annually on cooling buildings [8]. This accounts for about 3.9% of the total energy consumption of the buildings sector. Residential buildings consume approximately 0.68 PV-hours of energy per year, which is 2.9% of the total energy consumption of residential buildings. According to energy consumption forecasts in the buildings sector, cooling will become the largest energy consumer after 2050 [9].

Energy consumption in buildings is significantly influenced by technological, political and economic factors. The main ones include climate change, the growth of the world population, the relative efficiency of cooling equipment and the energy characteristics of buildings [10]. There are many studies investigating the dynamics of the increase in energy consumption for cooling in various sectors [8, 9, 11, 12]. Although the assumptions and boundary conditions used in these studies vary, the following general conclusion can be drawn: the demand for cooling in residential and commercial buildings will increase significantly in the future. According to the forecast of the demand for cooling in residential and commercial buildings until 2050, the annual consumption of energy for cooling in the residential sector will range from 0.9 to 2.61 PVt-h, with a high probability of 1.5 PVt-h. This corresponds to an increase of about 260% compared to current consumption. The most likely cooling demand in the residential sector by 2050 is 5.3 PVt-h, which corresponds to a 780% increase compared to current consumption [13].

The global market for cooling systems and refrigeration continues to grow, mainly in developing countries. By 2050, 37% of the total demand for electricity will be spent on air conditioning and cooling. It is known that there is a huge potential for cooling systems, which are solar thermal and photovoltaic systems using solar energy. Another factor in the development of solar cooling technology is that this system significantly reduces the basic demand for electricity, which is especially important for countries with high cooling demand and constraints in the power system. For example, currently 30% of the total energy consumed in buildings in India is spent on cooling, and during the summer peak load this value reaches 60% [14]. In the USA, during the hot sunny days of the summer, the peak load spent on air conditioning exceeds 70%. To protect the power system from such large peak loads, solar sorption systems are widely used. Solar sorption cooling is mainly used for medium and high-power plants (from 100 kW to several MW). For several years, China has been the world leader in the production of such environmentally friendly sorption plants.

The market for solar thermal cooling systems is also developing, for example, while 2,000 systems were commissioned in 2021, by the end of 2023, there were 598 large solar heating and cooling systems operating worldwide, with a total installed capacity of 2.3 GWth. Solar cooling technologies have been implemented mainly in China, Germany, Spain, Austria, and the Middle East, with the cooling capacity of individual facilities ranging from a few kilowatts to several megawatts.

Figure 1. Installation of solar heating and cooling devices

Figure 2. Solar cooling devices

The advantage of using solar energy in cooling processes is that solar radiation is available at the time when the demand for cooling is at its peak. In other words, the need for cooling arises when the sun is hot. Solar cooling saves money, i.e. it does not require the purchase of electricity at a very high price. In addition, it is possible to accumulate solar energy and use it for cooling in the evening and at night.

The electrical energy required to operate the pumps and gradients in a solar cooling system is relatively small, with an energy efficiency ratio (kWtie/kWtee) of 20 to 40 systems, depending on the climate. As can be seen, the electrical energy demand for air conditioning systems in buildings is reduced by up to 80% compared to conventional air conditioning systems.

The world's largest solar cooling system is located in Arizona, USA, and was commissioned in 2014. The system consists of 3.4 MW (4,865 m²) of solar thermal collectors, which transfer heat to a single efficient lithium device. This lithium bromide cooling device has a cooling capacity of 1.76 MW. In 2018, four other large solar cooling systems were installed in the world, two of which are located in Italy and one in Singapore, and use evacuated tube solar collectors. The fourth system is located in Jordan, and uses Fresnel collectors. The two largest solar cooling systems are located in Graz, Austria, and the other in the UAE, with a cooling capacity of 660 kW in Graz. Unfortunately, no new solar cooling systems were commissioned in 2021. In 2022, the world's largest solar cooling system was commissioned for a packaging factory in Izmir (Turkey). Its cooling capacity is 3.5 MW. The plant is equipped with solar thermal collectors with a total capacity of 2.5 MW (5,000 m²). The solar thermal system transfers heat to two lithium-bromine-based absorption chillers with cooling capacities of 1.4 and 2.1 MW. The COP of the two-stage absorption chillers reaches 1.4. Also, in 2022, three large solar cooling systems with a cooling capacity of 972 kW were commissioned. The total collector capacity of these systems is 1.86 MW, which corresponds to a collector area of

2,660 m². To date, according to statistics from 2025, two large-scale solar systems with a total capacity of 2.4 MW have been installed in the UAE. In addition, systems with a total capacity of up to 100 MW have been commissioned in China. Energy consumption for cooling residential buildings has tripled since 1990, which has had a significant impact on the electricity grid, greenhouse gas emissions and urban climate. As a result, 2024 was the hottest year on record and the fifth warmest year since 1800. As a result of the increase in the average surface temperature of the Earth, the demand for cooling is reaching a peak. The "True Zero Emissions by 2050" program has set three main tasks: 1) by 2030, 100% of new buildings with passive cooling systems with near-zero carbon emissions; 2) maintaining the set temperature of the indoor air at 24-25°C; 3) bringing the efficiency of cooling devices to a new level [15]. As the efficiency of cooling devices increases, the amount of carbon emissions from electricity generation also increases. According to the IEA, indirect CO₂

emissions from room cooling have tripled compared to 1990 and amounted to 1 Gt CO₂ in 2022. This value is 2% more than in 2021 [15]. To date, CO₂ emissions have reached 39.6 billion tonnes, an increase of 3.7% compared to 2021. For example, in New Zealand, a scenario has been adopted to reduce indirect CO₂ emissions from room cooling by 40% by 2030. The rate of emissions from space cooling has decreased significantly over the past decade, but the reduction should be three times faster by 2030. In addition to CO₂ emissions, space cooling also produces additional greenhouse gases from the leakage of refrigerants. These refrigerants are a major contributor to global warming, with a global warming potential that is a thousand times greater than CO₂. According to a 2023 report by the IEA, energy consumption for space cooling increased by 5% in 2022 compared to 2021. Since 2000, energy consumption for space cooling has increased by 4% per year, twice as fast as energy consumption for water heating [15]. The number of houses built between 2000 and 2025 exceeded 1.8 billion. If housing construction and energy demand continue at this rate, the electricity consumption for cooling will increase by 40% by 2030 [15]. In regions with high demand for cooling, the built-up area is expected to increase by 50% by 2030. In the last decade, the floor area of buildings has increased by about 60%, and the total area of buildings has reached 45 billion m². As a result, the share of local air conditioners is expected to increase from 37% to 45% by 2030 [15]. The adoption of proposed technologies for cooling rooms varies around the world, and the adoption of technologies in regions with high demand for cooling is very slow. For example, only 5% of households in sub-Saharan Africa are equipped with local air conditioners. This figure is less than 20% in India and Indonesia, and close to 30% in Mexico and Brazil. In comparison, this figure is over 85% in Japan, Korea, and the United States [15].

Conclusion.

One of the current global problems is global warming, which is causing great damage to nature. Climate change, of course, is caused by changes in the Earth's surface, in particular, an increase in the population, construction buildings, and the increase in industrial production. Manufacturing industries and factories require energy depending on their operating system, and as a result of this energy consumption, they emit various gases and other forms of waste into nature. This leads to climate change in nature. Or the depletion of natural resources can also lead to changes in the natural environment. The share of electricity generation, which is currently considered the main energy, in Uzbekistan accounts for 70% of the share of thermal power plants, and their main energy consumers can be fuels, in particular, gas, coal, fuel oil and other petroleum products. As a result of their burning, various toxic gases are released, in particular, CO₂ and CH₄ gases are released into the atmosphere and the ozone layer is depleted, causing global warming and an increase in toxic gases in the biosphere layer, resulting in disturbances in the plant world. Creating comfortable conditions in human habitats is one of the important tasks. Currently, global warming, which is considered a global problem, is being observed in the world, and it has increased by 1.2°C in recent years. To solve this problem, the use of renewable energy in cooling buildings, in particular the use of solar heating and cooling systems, is one of the alternative methods. This energy can save fossil fuels and achieve energy efficiency.

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